

ASSESSMENT OF RESIDUAL STRESSES IN THICK-WALLED GFRP SLIDING BEARING AFTER WINDING AND CURING

Alexander V. Bezmelnitsyn¹, Sergei B. Sapozhnikov²

¹Physics Department, National Research South Ural State University,
Chelyabinsk, Russian Federation

Email: Alexandr00786@gmail.com, web page: <http://www.en.susu.ac.ru>

²Physics Department, National Research South Ural State University,
Chelyabinsk, Russian Federation

Email: ssb@susu.ac.ru, web page: <http://www.en.susu.ac.ru>

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ABSTRACT

Thick fabric composite sliding bearing should be designed to endure high radial compressive loads and extend bearing life by use of self-lubricating modifiers in open porosity. As the thickness of the composite rings increases, technological residual stresses due to the anisotropic thermal expansion and shrinkage of fabric composites also increase, which induces inter-laminar failure. Therefore, the accurate estimation of the residual stresses is indispensable for the development of thick fabric composite rings.

To understand the nature of residual stresses in GFRP rings the dilatometry analysis was carried out and CTE distribution through-thickness in the hoop and axial direction was obtain.

For determining volume fraction of filaments and matrix into the threads of GFRP we used an optical method. Observation of slices in optical microscope allowed us to determine the degree of curvature of fibres and the thickening of inner ring layers for further 3D modelling.

The structure of the woven composite ring was modelled by using impregnated unidirectional (UD microplastic) threads and repeated unit cell (RUC). Modulus of elasticity, Poisson's ratios and coefficients of thermal expansion at micro-scale, macro-scale and meso-scale were calculated by FEA (ANSYS Workbench).

1 INTRODUCTION

Reliability and durability of many construction elements depend on the performance of the friction units. Along with the traditional materials in the manufacture of slide bearings (babbitt, bronze, etc.), manufacturers use a variety of composite materials [1].

Intense static and dynamic loads cause irreversible plastic deformations in the sliding bearing, which lead to vibrations and wear increasing. Sliding bearings based on glass-fibre prepreg do not have of these problems because of high transverse elasticity. Composite sliding bearings obtained by winding may have a high open porosity that reduce compliance and, respectively, contact stresses.

GFRP sliding bearings with open porosity filed by lubricant, which will be realized during work of friction unit, not require of lubricant-delivery system. They are cheap and easy to use and maintenance.

Tension during the winding, curing and cooling processes have a significant effect on the distribution mechanical properties of the ring and residual radial stresses after manufacturing [2-4]. When the value the residual stress exceeds the strength of the polymer matrix in the sliding bearing may have macro-cracks leading to delamination. In addition, residual stresses often lead to a change in the size and shape of the ring. Moreover, a differences in a composite bushing microstructure effect on the elastic moduli, thermal expansion coefficients etc. [5-7].

For analysis mechanical and thermal properties as well as the evaluation of residual technological stresses thick-walled wound rings, we used multi-scale modelling [8-17]. This method is based on modelling of material properties at the different scale levels (micro, meso, and macro). The micro

scale consisting of the monofilament fibre and matrix. The meso scale consists of the RUC for the fabric, which represents the behaviour of the woven composite material. Macro-model reflects the relationship between the layers that form GFRP rings. The results from the different micromechanics schemes were compared with experimental data to evaluate the applicability of the computational model.

2 MATERIAL AND TECHNOLOGY

Tube thickness was formed by winding in the hoop direction on a solid steel mandrel (90 mm diameter and 300 mm long). The material used in this study is plane-weave glass fabric of thickness about 0.24 mm prepreg with epoxy/phenolic resin as matrix and acetone as a solvent and open porosity producer. Tension force of tape was about 5 kilo/cm to provide consolidation of prepreg on mandrel during circumferential winding. After winding the mandrel wrapped over by cotton tape with tension force about 6 kilo/cm. Typical oven curing process is: 90 °C/2 hrs, 120 °C/2 hrs, 160 °C /8 hrs and cooling with oven (about 5-10 °C/hr for relaxation of fibre/matrix manufacturing stresses). Open porosity is needed to place the grease for full life of ring exploitation.

The GFRP tube were precisely cut into rings' widths of 15 mm (Fig. 1) using disk cutter.

Figure 1: GFRP ring.

The average density of GFRP rings is 1.48 g/cm³, glass-fibre volume fraction is about 46%, voids are about 23% and matrix is about 31%. These results were obtained in previous work [18].

3 EXPERIMENTS

3.1 Determination of volume fraction of filaments and matrix of microplastic

The optical method aimed to examination of the composite cross-sectional area to determine the fibre and resin volume fractions. Inherent to this method is the assumption that the fibre and resin cross-sectional areas are uniform along the length (perpendicular to the cross section).

For this purposes we cut out segment of the ring and sawed off a thin slice (thickness of 0.2mm). Then the surface slice was observed under a transmitted light microscope and the image is magnified 50X. The microscope has a high-definition camera, which is interfaced with the computer system. There is prior auto positioning stage that is also connected to the computer system. The filaments appear as dark grey regions in the image (Fig. 2). The computer assigns a false colour to each shade of grey and the percent area is calculated based on the number of pixels for each colour for each frame. The resin volume is calculated based on the remaining area fraction.

Figure 2: Micrograph of the cross-section of thin slice.

Glass-fibre volume fraction is about 68.7% and matrix is about 31.3%.

3.2 Characterization of the wave geometry

The wave of the fabric was determined from direct observation of the bearing mesostructure. Samples were cut from the GFRP ring such that the major axis was parallel to either the warp or fill bundle directions, mounted in an epoxy-moulding compound, polished and viewed at with an optical microscope. Representative mesostructure of the samples with voids is shown in Figure 3.

a)

b)

Figure 3: Mesostructure of GFRP ring a) warp yarns parallel to the page, fill yarns perpendicular, b) fill yarns parallel to the page, and warp yarns perpendicular.

3.2 Thermal expansion test

The ring was cut into five samples of the through-thickness of the hoop and width direction (Fig. 4). Specimens with dimensions of 1.75×3.5×17.5 mm of the hoop direction and 1.75×3.5×13.6 mm of the width direction were used for thermal expansion tests. For each specimen two repeat tests were performed.

Figure 4: Samples location to cut for measuring CTE.

The NETZSCH DIL402C dilatometer was employed to measure CTE of composites samples. In these experiments, measurements were made by ramping the sample temperature from 22 to 90 °C at a rate of 2 °C /min and then ramping the sample temperature at the same rate back to 22 °C. If the difference between the transducer output at the beginning and end of the experiment was greater than 5% of the total change then the experiment was repeated again until good agreement was achieved: in general, once the rig had attained thermal equilibrium, repeatable results were measured. An average was then taken of the change in length for the two temperature step experiments (i.e. for the heating and cooling cycle), yielding an average value of the thermal expansion coefficient in the temperature range 22-90 °C.

CTE (α) was calculated from the following equation:

$$CTE(\alpha) = \frac{\Delta L/L}{\Delta T},$$

where L is the original length of the sample, ΔL is changing length of the sample and ΔT is the temperature change.

We could determine CTE and its distribution into ring's thickness (Fig. 5).

Figure 5: CTE distribution of the through-the-thickness of the ring.

The curves represented in the Figure 5 show that CTE is distributed unevenly of through-thickness direction.

3.3 Radial tension

Mechanical tests were performed by means of universal testing machine INSTRON 5882. Applied load was measured by 5 kN load cell and sample deflection – by clamp displacement. Rate of displacement was 10 mm/min. Quasi-static tensile tests were conducted at room temperature. Tension of ring creates significant bending moment in cross section that increases of radius of ring curvature and creates transverse tensile stress and delamination (Fig. 6). Results of the experiments are shown in Table 1.

Figure 6: Tension ring test.

Specimen number	1	2	3	4	5
Failure loads (kN)	7.7	8.6	8.1	8.1	8.0

Table 1: Failure loads of the specimen.

During the quasi-static loading, the specimens deformed elastically before the initiation of fracture load at 8.1 kN.

3.4 Transversal tension

The bearing ring was cut into five samples (15×15×9 mm) (Fig. 7). Each specimen was glued to the special T-shaped grips (Fig. 8) with room cured epoxy resin.

Figure 7: Specimens for the transversal tensile test.

Figure 8: Fixture used in tension experiment.

Transverse tensile tests for the specimens were operated on universal testing machine INSTRON 5882. Applied load was measured by 5 kN load cell and sample deflection – by clamp displacement. Quasi-static tensile tests were performed with a test speed of 10 mm/min up to failure.

The tensile stress σ was determined as the ratio of axial force to cross-sectional area of specimens. Results of the experiments are shown in Table 2.

Specimen number	1	2	3	4	5
Rupture stress (MPa)	14.6	12.4	13.9	10.9	11.0

Table 2: Rupture stress of the specimen.

An average fracture stress is $\sigma \approx 12.6$ MPa.

4 FE MODELLING

4.1 Micro-modelling

For determination of elastic and thermal properties of microplastic there is studied micromechanical model with use of finite element analysis. To determine longitudinal and transversal properties of microplastic, three dimensional analysis was implemented. Representative unit cell of 3D models were created using SolidWorks (Fig. 9). The representative unit cell used for the analysis is a cylinder, which is inserted in a cube with unit dimension. Fibres are assumed to have a square packing arrangement. The radius of the cylinder is determined with respect to fibre volume fraction of the composite. Using the advantage of symmetry, only 1/8 of the unit cell is modelled to describe the behaviours of the unit cell for the FEA.

Figure 9: 3D models of the microplastic (a) and boundary conditions (b).

The 'frictionless' boundary conditions were used for the flat edges. The 'no separation' contacts were used for connecting the cell and rigid bodies.

Assuming that each phase is homogeneous, isotropic and linearly elastic were found elastic and thermal properties of microplastic.

Table 3 shows material properties of the glass fibre and resin, which were the input properties in FE micro-model.

Material	E(GPa)	$\alpha(10^{-6}/C^0)$	ν (Poisson ratio)
Epoxy resin	3.5	63.0	0.35
Glass fibre	72.0	5.4	0.3

Table 3: Mechanical properties of resin and glass-fibre.

FEA-calculate of all thermal (α_1, α_2) and mechanical (E, G and ν – 9 parameters) properties of UD of cell (yarn) shown in Table 4.

E_z (GPa)	$E_x = E_y$ (GPa)	$G_{xz} = G_{yz}$ (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	$\nu_{xz} = \nu_{yz}$	ν_{xy}	$\alpha_z(10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C})$	$\alpha_x = \alpha_y(10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C})$
50.4	21.6	6.0	8.7	0.303	0.243	7.4	30.6

Table 4: Properties of yarn obtained from FEA simulation.

These results uses below in FEA-modelling of impregnated UD threads of plane weave fabric. These parameters are in good agreement with the analytical ones obtained from [18].

4.1 Meso-modelling

In this case, the woven composite ring was modelled using a repeated unit cell (RUC). Furthermore, due to symmetry of the microstructure, one quarter of the RUC is sufficient for analysis using mirror boundary conditions.

The meso-mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced composites are primarily dependent on the fibre preform geometry, accurate descriptions and reasonable approximations of the macro-architecture can facilitate the analysis work of their mechanical properties.

Observation of slices in optical microscope allowed determining the curvature of fibres and thickening of layers (Fig. 3) for further FE modelling (Fig. 10). The boundary conditions are the same as in paragraph 4.1.

Figure 10: 3D model of the woven fabric RUC (a) and boundary conditions (b).

The unidirectional yarns have orthotropic behaviours, which require defining local coordinate systems for each yarn. Furthermore, the crimp of the yarn causes the local fibre axis to rotate with respect to the global coordinate system along the length of the yarn, which causes the effective modulus in the global direction to vary. Therefore, it was necessary to assign a local coordinate system to each element such that the local fibre axis is always parallel to the local Z direction along the length of the yarn (Fig. 11).

Figure 11: Yarn geometry showing local coordinate systems for definition of orthotropic constitutive material behaviour in woven fabric unit cell.

Results from determination of thermal and mechanical behaviours of RUC are shown in Table 5.

E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	E_z (GPa)	G_{xz} (GPa)	G_{yz} (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	ν_{xz}	ν_{yz}	α_x ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	α_y ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	α_z ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)
23.3	16.9	8.1	2.1	2.4	4.2	0.21	0.37	0.15	14.8	18.0	8.9

Table 5: Properties of woven fabric RUC obtained from FEA simulation.

4.2 Macro-modelling

Having developed a numerical model for the RUC, the next step is to create the GFRP ring model with cylindrical orthotropic properties. Thermal and mechanical properties of orthotropic materials were obtained from RUC. To verify the chosen model must be to compare the numerical simulation and experiment (tension ring test). Using the advantage of symmetry, only 1/4 of the ring is modelled to describe the behaviour. Results of the FEA are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Transverse stress under radial tension

The FEA results show that the maximum tensile stress is ~ 11 MPa in the radial direction. Furthermore, experimental results obtained from radial tension tests of the rings (Fig. 6) showed disagreement with ones obtained under transversal tension (Fig. 7), this is due to unaccounted residual stresses after manufacturing.

When the ring is removed off the mandrel there are induced residual stresses in the ring due to curing the ring and cooling down to the room temperature. It can be possible to calculate radial tension residual stress after curing and cooling by using of elastic and thermal data obtained from micro- and meso-FEA models. Thus, ΔT used for the calculation was -120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Results of numerical experiments with FEA with cylindrical coordinate system shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Residual stress after cooling

Numerical simulation of cooling shows that the value of residual stress $\sigma_r \approx 2$ MPa.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we investigated the structure of the thick-walled GFRP sliding bearing both experimentally and numerically.

The dilatometry analysis shows that that CTE is distributed irregularly in through-thickness direction that can be explained by difference of resin content through ring thickness due to fibre's curvature variables in hoop direction.

Representative volume elements (RVE) for yarn (micro level) and woven fabric (meso level) were created using the experimental data about real micro- and mesostructure of composite. Multi-scale FE modelling framework was developed to evaluate the mechanical, thermal properties of composite ring. Model allow to estimate residual curing stresses as well as ring deformation during tension tests and obtained results are in a good agreement with experimental data.

Obtained results can be used to predict physical behaviours of fabric reinforced composite and residual stresses in thick-walled composite ring as the bearing part.

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